

The Effect of Media Exposure on Visual Discrimination Ability of Elementary School Children Age

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 26, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: December 31, 2021</p> <p>Keywords : Visual Discrimination, Media Exposure, Male/Female School Children, Rural/Urban Govt. And private schools, Elementary Education</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5812284</p>	<p><i>This study was carried out to investigate the effect of media exposure on the visual discrimination ability of elementary school children in District Swabi, Khyber Pukhtoonkhwa. The main objectives of study were: (i) to investigate effect of media exposure on visual discrimination ability of elementary school children aged 4-8 years, (ii) to examine effect of media exposure on visual discrimination ability of rural and urban elementary school children age 4-8, (iii) to explore the effect of media exposure on visual discrimination ability of male and female elementary school children age 4-8 years, (iv) to compare the effect of media exposure on visual discrimination ability of Government and private elementary school children age 4-8 years, Six hundred and forty students of g elementary schools were taken as sample of the study. An empirical research design was used to conduct the study. For collection of data, questionnaire, and worksheets were developed and data were analyzed statistically through SPSS by applying mean, percentage, and median, to get the results of the study. It was observed that media exposure has a positive effect on visual discrimination ability of elementary school children. The research will be beneficial for elementary school children, teachers, curriculum planners, and future researchers.</i></p>

Introduction

Media exposure

The media includes both electronic and print, as internet, television, radio, newspapers, and magazines. Understanding and measuring how people use or are "exposed" to media is essential for understanding communication effects. This is especially difficult in light of the increasingly divided media landscape and the shift to online environments where people are exposed to or create a vast array of messages at any time and from any location. Simultaneously, the transition to advanced conditions likewise opens up a progression of freedoms to build our insight about media use, including by means of aloof estimation through following information, or getting reactions continuously.

Children are experiencing childhood in an advanced age with expanding openness to TV and touchscreen gadgets. Kids grow up encompassed by media including books, TV, and all the more as of late, portable touchscreen gadgets. Time went through drawing in with screen media impacts parent–youngster cooperation. At the point when TV is on behind the scenes, the quality, and amount of guardians' communication diminishes (Kirkorian *et al.*, 2014). Moreover, observational information exhibit that guardians' versatile touchscreen gadget use can lessen parent's consideration and commitment with their kids (Radesky *et al.*, 2014). These worries don't stretch out to kids' openness to books. Reading normally inspires discourse input from guardians (Nyhout and O'Neill, 2014)

VISUAL DISCRIMINATION

Vision is our most predominant sense, from which we infer the majority of our data about the world. From the light that enters the eye and the handling in the mind that follows we can sense where things are, the way they move, and what they are, from the light that enters the eyes and handling in the mind that follows (Swanston, and Wade, 2013)

Visual insight is one of major perceptual faculties in human existence. Visual insight generally confirms that people build a word or picture and interpret it (Chandler, 2004). Vision is preeminent among all the insight exercises, as people consistently allot importance or exercise their own visual ideas.

Visual discrimination is a fundamental piece of perceptual exercises and is framed in the cerebrum through the eyes (Nikolajeva, & Scott, 2013)

The expertise of visual preparing ought to be sub-partitioned into the part abilities of visual consideration, visual separation, visual memory, and visual consecutive memory. The ability of word acknowledgment requires both hear-able and visual discrimination abilities. Kids need to segregate outwardly

between the states of graphemes and words as well as articulating sounds. They additionally need to foster the expertise of submitting a grapheme or an entire word to their memory. Kids with helpless momentary recollections might battle to recover data from their memory and this will hinder their advancement in word identification. Creating visual abilities, including the advancement of visual memory, may be important regardless of whether hear-able abilities are reliable. An appraisal battery which evaluates visual discrimination may incorporate, regardless of whether kids can outwardly separate the odd thing from a bunch of objects. This ability could formatively be evaluated utilizing photos, line drawing, or outlines in that succession. The ability of visual memory could be evaluated corresponding to whether kids can review two items which are shown then in this manner concealed away from the youngster. The scope of articles could continuously be expanded and afterward at long last the ability of visual consecutive memory could be surveyed to recognize whether kids can remember the items and their relating request inside a set. These expertise are pre-essential abilities for reading. (Glazzard, 2017).

ELEMENTARY EDUCATION

An individual is a positive resource and a valuable public asset which should be loved, sustained, and created with delicacy and care, combined with dynamism.

The significant effects of elementary education are especially perceptible to the extent a decline in destitution, improvement in money flow, prosperity and the empowering status of the general population, its contrary relationship with reproduction, and expansion in populace, positive relationship with of family planning, and with the overall social, political and financial progression and the overall individual fulfillment (McMohan, 2010).

The main extensive stretches of an individual's schooling are during the rudimentary years, as adolescents can get instruction and preparing during these early years (Avraamova, 2014).

It is the elementary schooling which establishes solid framework for the kid's physical, scholarly, passionate, and social turn of events. Essential (5-11 years) of a child life are spent in primary schools and in middle schools (11-13 years) age bunch. The quintessence of the objective is for like clockwork old to have procured establishment abilities like the capacity to peruse and compose with familiarity, numeracy, cognizance, examination, thinking and social abilities like collaboration. Similarly, elementary schooling ought to ingrain in kids fortitude, certainty, interest, autonomy, genius, versatility, persistence, and comprehension (Kumari, 2020).

Universalization of elementary education is the bedrock of improvement and progress of any general public. As indicated by Article 25-A, of the Constitution of Pakistan, it is the obligation of the state to give free and mandatory training to all the populace between 5 to 16 years old (UNESCO, 2011). Widespread essential schooling can't be accomplished without the coordinated endeavors of the relative multitude of social foundations and partners. (Zakar *et al.*, 2013).

LITERAURE REVIEW

Research interests of media exposure and children's improvement, has expanded because of improvement of the Internet and advanced imaging innovation, of with the fast development of innovation, youngsters are extremely drawn in by TVs, cell phones, and PC (Personal Computers) and tablet-based games. The extent of time spent by kids on screen-based relaxation exercises and the recurrence of utilizing tablet in youngsters have expanded. (Lin, 2019)

As Sahin and Cimen (2011) proposed, a frequent use of PC pointing game will advance children's visual-discrimination ability (Kim *et al.*, 2018)

The digital pointing game is found as a valuable apparatus to draw out the hopeful change in daily existence and visual discrimination related learning circumstance for youngsters with serious mental incapacities with or without educator's inclusion.

Studies have shown that children's inspiration and interest in learning can be upgraded by applying technology to training (Zevenbergen and Logan, 2008).

Visual improvements given by computer games boost visual discrimination ability, the speed of visual checking, and specific consideration (Johnson, 2012). Two meta-investigations of the impacts of computer game preparing on visual and spatial discrimination ability show that playing computer games has constructive outcomes (Powers *et al.*, 2013; Stanmore *et al.*, 2017). Studies propose that computer games may emphatically influence range of visual discrimination abilities.

The majority of the computer applications for improving kids' visual insight and discrimination abilities included liveliness or animation pictures. The children were thus deprived of an ideal opportunity for inclusion in practical conditions and of the opportunity to gain insight into noticing objects in different conditions (AAP, 2016)

The outcomes showed that kids' visual discrimination capacities were improved fundamentally with the experience of computer games. Furthermore, the improvement of kids' visual discrimination ability differed

altogether as indicated by computer games' type. No association impacts were found between a kid's sex and the computer games' type. (Ju, and Eun, 2003)

The media have both positive and adverse consequences on the families and on the connections among kids and guardians. Media impacts are in reality considerably more perplexing than involved in the basic division among negative and beneficial outcomes (Livingstone 2007).

There is no proof from research that TV and portable touchscreen gadget use has a positive, or an inconvenient, impact (Taylor *et al.*, 2018).

Analysts examining the impact of media have discovered unobtrusive negative connections, or none by any means, between the all-out time youngsters spend seeing TV and their school accomplishment. Exploration that considers important attributes of the young students, like their IQ and financial status, ordinarily tracks down no huge connection between long periods of TV survey and accomplishment (Li, 2017). Level of intelligence, specifically, assumes a huge part in the relationship between TV watching and accomplishment. The measure of time spent review TV additionally seems to impact accomplishment for kids from various financial foundations in an unexpected way. Watching a great deal of TV is contrarily connected with accomplishment for privileged kids (Velicu, and Marinescu, 2019). Yet, TV seeing is decidedly related (or not related by any stretch of the imagination) with accomplishment for impeded youngsters or those with restricted capability in English (Kim, and So, 2012).

At the point when analysts look at the general significance of media content and complete time went through with media, they track down that content matters more. For instance, observational proof emphatically upholds the idea that top notch instructive programming has positive advantages for kids' scholastic abilities, scholarly commitment, and mentalities toward learning (Schmidt, & Anderson, 2006).

There are two primary speculations on the media use and scholarly accomplishment. One is the inspiration theory, which upholds that all around planned media programs upgrade young people's scholastic accomplishment. The other is the decrease speculation, which thinks the young people who saw more TV will in general invest less energy doing schoolwork, examining, and reading (Nary, 2004).

Researchers finish up the connection between the media use and scholarly accomplishment is curvilinear (Li, 2017).

Statement of the Problem

The problem of the study is to investigate effect of media exposure on the visual discrimination ability among elementary school children of different age group 4 – 8 years in, District Swabi, Khyber Pukhtoonkhwa (Pakistan).

Objectives of the study

- To investigate effect of media exposure on visual discrimination ability of elementary school children aged 4-8 years.
- To examine effect of media exposure on visual discrimination ability of rural and urban elementary school children age 4-8.
- To explore the effect of media exposure on visual discrimination ability of male and female elementary school children age 4-8 years
- To compare the effect of media exposure on visual discrimination ability of Government and private elementary school children age 4-8 years,

Method and Procedure

This study was designed to investigate the effect of media exposure on visual discrimination ability of elementary school children of age 4-8 years. To achieve the objectives of the study, the following research methods were used.

Population

The population of the study comprised of all the students studying in government schools. A total of 2.46 million male and 1.91 million female students were enrolled from grade 1-5 in all government schools in Khyber Pukhtoonkhwa. Govt. of Khyber Pukhtoonkhwa (2018).

Sample

The sample of the study was selected from two government rural schools (GGPS Shahmansoor), (GPS Shahmansoor), two government urban schools, (GGPS Zaida I and II), two private urban schools (The City School Swabi Campus) and (Frontier Public School Zaida) and two private rural schools (Abdali Model School) and (The Superior School Shahmansoor) using the purposeful sampling method A total of 640 students were selected. From each school 80 students were selected from age groups. Among these age groups 4-8 years, 20 students were of age 48 months to 60 months, 20 students were of age 61 months to 72 months, 20 students were of 73 to 84 months, and 20 of 85 months to 96 months. These students were randomly selected whose parents/guardian filled the questionnaire with prior approval of school administration. In the government urban and rural schools 20 girls and 20 boys were selected from each age group in every school, while in private rural and urban schools 10 boys and 10 girls were selected from each age group as there was co-education in these

schools. In this way a total of 640 students were observed for their visual discrimination ability according to their age group, socio economic conditions, and media exposure. According to Gay (2009) if the size of the population is in thousands or in millions, then a sample size of 400 will be acceptable.

Research Design

An empirical research design was used to conduct study to investigate the effect of media exposure on visual discrimination ability of elementary school children.

(Ahmad, 2016)

Research Instrument

Twenty five worksheets for upper case letters, 25 worksheets for lower case letters, and 25 worksheets for 3 letter words were used as research instrument. Letter page sized 8.5” *11” with printing words and letters in Calibri bold 72 sized fonts each with two columns in the 1st column was printed the alphabet\word to be matched and in 2nd column were given 3 choices matching to the sample. The correct option was randomized for each matching letter\word.

Procedure of the Study

The sample children of age 4-5 and 5-6 were given 25 worksheets of three matching to sample of uppercase letters. The children of age 6-7 were given 25 worksheets of 3 choices matching to sample of lowercase letters. The children of age 7-8 were given 25 worksheets of 3 letter words.

Students in each school and each age group were given the relevant worksheet, with prior instructions in national language, in case students were not able to pick the instructions they were instructed in regional language, Pashto. After giving clear instructions children were given 30 minutes to match letter\words with the sample with the specific word.

Scoring of Responses

Each child’s correct matching response was given ‘1’ mark for each correct response and ‘0’ mark for each incorrect response. There were total ‘25’ marks

Following observation sheet was used for scoring the data.

S.No.	Name	Age in months	Correct response	Wrong response	Score
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Twenty five worksheets for upper case letters, 25 worksheets for lower case letters, and 25 worksheets for 3 letter words were used as research instrument.

Data Collection

Data was collected through worksheets, observation sheets, and proformas to check students’ age and visual discrimination relevancy.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed through Statistical package for Social Sciences (SPSS) by applying statistical formulae of mean, median, and percentage.

Table 1. Scores and percentage of Media exposure of school children of urban and rural schools (N=160)

Age group	Urban Schools		Rural Schools	
	Yes	No	Yes	No
4-5 years	40 (50%)	40 (50%)	20 (25%)	60 (75%)
5-6 years	36 (45%)	44 (55%)	40 (50%)	40 (50%)
6-7 years	32 (40%)	48 (60%)	27 (33.8%)	53 (66.3%)
7-8 years	39 (48.8%)	41 (51.2%)	25 (31.2%)	55 (68.8%)

Table 1 shows that in urban schools 40 (50%) children of age group of 4-5 years old have media exposure and 40 (50%) has no media exposure while in rural schools, 20 (25%) children has media exposure in the age group of 4-5 years old and 60 (75%) children has no media exposure. In the age group of 5-6 years, 36 (45%) children has media exposure, 44 (55%) has no media exposure in urban school children whereas 40 (50%) has media exposure and 40 (50%) has no media exposure in rural school children. In age group of 6-7 years old, children 32 (40%) has media exposure, 48 (60%) has no media exposure in urban schools children and 27 (33.8%) has media exposure, 53 (66.3%) has no media exposure in rural schools children. Whereas, in the age group of 7-8 years old, 39 (48.8%) children has media exposure, 41 (51.2%) has no media exposure in urban school children and 25 (31.2%) children has media exposure, 55 (68.8%) has no media exposure in the rural school children. It means that comparatively children of urban schools had better media exposure in the age groups 4-5 years, 6-7 years, and 7-8 years than the children of rural school in these age brackets. Only in age group 5-6 year's rural school children has better media exposure than urban school children.

It is concluded that in all the age groups, maximum children of urban schools have better media exposure as compared to rural school children.

Table 2. Scores and percentage of Media exposure of school children of government and private schools (N=160)

Age group	Government Schools		Private Schools	
	Yes	No	Yes	No
4-5 years	1 (1.3%)	79 (98.7%)	59 (73.7%)	21 (26.3%)
5-6 years	1 (1.3%)	79 (98.7%)	75 (93.7%)	5 (6.3%)
6-7 years	0 (0%)	80 (100%)	58 (72.5%)	22 (27.5%)
7-8 years	1 (1.3%)	79 (98.7%)	63 (78.7%)	17 (21.3%)

Table 2 shows that in government schools maximum children 79 (98.7%) has no media exposure while in private schools, maximum children 59 (73.3%) has media exposure in the age group of 4-5 years old while 21 (26.3%) children has no media exposure. In the age group of 5-6 years, maximum children 79 (98.7%) has no media exposure in government elementary schools, 75 (93.7%) has media exposure in private school children whereas in the age group of 6-7 years, maximum children of government schools 80 (100%) has no media exposure and in private school children 58 (72.5%) has media exposure. In age group of 7-8 years old, maximum children 79 (98.7%) in government school children has no media exposure and maximum children 63(78.7%) in private schools has media exposure.

It means that in all four age groups, maximum children of private elementary school children have media exposure greater than the children of government school who have minor media exposure.

Table 3 Scores and percentage of Media exposure of school children of male and female schools (N=160)

Age group	Male Schools		Female Schools	
	Yes	No	Yes	No
4-5 years	29 (36.3%)	51 (63.8%)	32 (40%)	48 (60%)
5-6 years	38 (47.5%)	42 (52.5%)	43 (53.8%)	37 (46.2%)
6-7 years	30	50	31	51

	(37.5%)	(62.5%)	(38.2%)	(63.8%)
7-8 years	31	49	33	47
	(38.8%)	(61.2%)	(41.2%)	(58.8%)

Table 3 shows that in male schools maximum children 51 (63.8%) has no media exposure, 29(36.3%)has media exposure while in female schools, maximum children 48(60%) has no media exposure and 32(40%)has media exposure in the age group of 4-5 years old. In the age group of 5-6 years, maximum children 42 (52.5%) has no media exposure in male elementary schools, 38(47.5%) has media exposure in private school children while maximum children in female schools 43(53.8%) has media exposure whereas in the age group of 6-7 years, maximum children of male schools 50(62.5%) has no media exposure, only 30(37.5%) has media exposure while in female school children 51(63.8%) has no media exposure, 31(38.2%) has media exposure. In age group of 7-8 years old, maximum children 49(61.2%) in male school children has no media exposure, only 31(38.8%) has media exposure while maximum children 47(58.8%) in female schools has no media exposure and 33 (41.2%) has media exposure.

It means that media exposure is better in female school children as compared to male schools children.

Table 4. Media and internet exposure of Urban and Rural elementary school children

S. No.		Urban	Rural	Total	Grand Total
1	Children exposed to media and internet aged 4 to 5 years	42 (66.67%)	21 (33.33%)	63 (100%)	160
2	Children not exposed to media and internet aged 4 to 5 years	38 (39.18%)	59 (60.82%)	97 (100%)	
3	Children exposed to media and internet aged 5 to 6 years	38 (50%)	38 (50%)	76 (100%)	160
4	Children not exposed to media and internet aged 5 to 6 years	42 (50%)	42 (50%)	84 (100%)	
5	Children exposed to media and internet aged 6 to 7 years	32 (54.24%)	27 (45.76%)	59 (100%)	160
6	Children not exposed to media and internet aged 6 to 7 years have visual discrimination ability of lower case letters	48 (47.52%)	53 (52.48%)	101 (100%)	
7	Children exposed to media and internet aged 7 to 8 years have visual discrimination ability of simple 3 letter words	39 (61.90%)	24 (38.10%)	63 (100%)	160
8	Children not exposed to media and internet aged 7 to 8 years have visual discrimination ability of simple 3 letters word	41 (42.27%)	56 (57.73%)	97 (100%)	
	Total	320	320	640	640

Table 4 indicates that out of 63 children, 66.67 % children aged 4-5 years of urban schools have exposure to media and internet and in rural schools, 33.33 % have exposure in media and internet. Whereas, in rural school children, 60.82 % had no exposure of media and internet and 39.18 % had no exposure to media and internet in urban school children.

In urban schools, 50 % children in age group of 5-6 years, 54.24 percent in age group of 6-7 years and 61.90 % in age group of 7-8 years had media and internet exposure while in rural schools, 50 % children in age 5-6 years, 45.76 % in age 6-7 years and 38.10 % in age 7-8 years had media and internet exposure.

In urban schools, 50 % children in age 5-6 years, 47.52 % in age 6-7 years and 42.27 % in age 7-8 years had no media and internet exposure while in rural schools, 50 % children in age 5-6 years, 52.48 % in age 6-7 years and 57.73 % in age 7-8 years had no media and internet exposure.

It means that majority of the children in urban schools except age group of 5-6 years had better media and internet exposure as compared to rural school children.

Table 5. Media and internet exposure of government and Private Schools children

S. No.		Govt.	Private	Total	Grand Total
1	Children exposed to media and internet aged 4 to 5 years	1 (1.67%)	59 (98.33%)	60 (100%)	160
2	Children not exposed to media and internet aged 4 to 5 years	79 (79 %)	21 (21%)	100 (100%)	
3	Children exposed to media and internet aged 5 to 6 years	1 (1.30%)	76 (98.7%)	77 (100%)	160
4	Children not exposed to media and internet aged 5 to 6 years	79 (95.18%)	4 (4.82%)	83 (100%)	
5	Children exposed to media and internet aged 6 to 7 years	0 (0%)	61 (96.83%)	61 (100%)	160
6	Children not exposed to media and internet aged 6 to 7 years have visual discrimination ability of lower case letters	80 (80.81%)	19 (19.19%)	99 (100%)	
7	Children exposed to media and internet aged 7 to 8 years have visual discrimination ability of simple 3 letter words	1 (1.56%)	63 (98.44%)	64 (100%)	160
8	Children not exposed to media and internet aged 7 to 8 years have visual discrimination ability of simple 3 letters word	79 (82.29%)	17 (17.71%)	96 (100%)	
	Total	320	320	640	640

Table 5 shows that in government schools, 1.67 % children in age 4-5 years, 1.3 % in age 5-6 years, 0 % in age 6-7 years and 1.56 % in age 7-8 years had media and internet exposure while in private schools, 98.33 % children in age 4-5 years, 98.7 % in age 5-6 years, 96.83 % in age 6-7 years and 98.44 % in age 7-8 years had media and internet exposure to the children of elementary schools.

In government schools, 79 % children in age 4-5 years, 95.18 % in age 5-6 years, 80.81 % in age 6-7 years and 82.29 % in age 7-8 years had no media and internet exposure while in private schools, 21 % children in age 4-5 years, 4.82 % in age 5-6 years, 19.19 % in age 6-7 years and 17.71 % in age 7-8 years had no media and internet exposure to the children.

It means that majority of the children in private schools had better media and internet exposure as compared to government school children.

Table 6. Gender based (boys and girls) media and internet exposure of school children

S. No.		Boys	Girls	Total	Grand Total
1	Children exposed to media and internet aged 4 to 5 years	28 (45.90 %)	33 (54.10 %)	61 (100 %)	160
2	Children not exposed to media and internet aged 4 to 5 years	52 (52.53%)	47 (47.47%)	99 (100%)	
3	Children exposed to media and internet aged 5 to 6 years	38 (51.35%)	36 (48.65%)	74 (100%)	160
4	Children not exposed to media and internet aged 5 to 6 years	42 (48.84%)	44 (51.16%)	86 (100%)	
5	Children exposed to media and internet aged 6 to 7 years	30 (50.85%)	29 (49.15%)	59 (100%)	160
6	Children not exposed to media and internet aged 6 to 7 years have visual discrimination ability of lower case letters	50 (49.50%)	51 (50.50%)	101 (100%)	
7	Children exposed to media and internet aged 7 to 8 years have visual discrimination ability of simple 3 letter words	31 (48.44%)	33 (51.56%)	64 (100%)	160
8	Children not exposed to media and internet aged 7 to 8 years have visual discrimination ability of simple 3 letters word	49 (51.04%)	47 (48.96%)	96 (100%)	

Total	320	320	640	640
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Table 6 reveals that in boys schools, 45.9 % children in age 4-5 years, 51.35 % in age 5-6 years, 50.85 % in age 6-7 years and 48.44 % in age 7-8 years had media and internet exposure while in girls' schools, 54.10 % children in age 4-5 years, 48.65 % in age 5-6 years, 49.15 % in age 6-7 years and 51.56 % in age 7-8 years had media and internet exposure to the children.

In boys schools, 52.53 % children in age 4-5 years, 48.84 % in age 5-6 years, 49.5 % in age 6-7 years and 51.04 % in age 7-8 years had no media and internet exposure while in girls' schools, 47.47 % children in age 4-5 years, 51.16 % in age 5-6 years, 50.5 % in age 6-7 years and 48.96 % in age 7-8 years had no media and internet exposure to the children.

It means that majority of the children in boys schools had better media and internet exposure in age group of 5-6 years and 6-7 years as compared to girls school children while in age group of 4-5 years and 7-8 years girls school children had better as compared boys schools.

DISCUSSION

Aim of the present study was to investigate the effect of media exposure on visual discrimination ability of elementary school children and to compare gender (girls, boys), locality (urban, rural), and schools (government, private).

The study showed that for all the age groups maximum number of children of the urban schools have better media exposure as compared to rural school children except for age group 5-6 years (Table. 1 & 4).

Among all the four groups' maximum children of private elementary schools have are more exposed to media as compared to government schools children (Table. 2 & 5).

Majority of the children in boys schools had better media and internet exposure in age group of 5-6 years and 6-7 years as compared to girls school children while in age group of 4-5 years and 7-8 years girls school children had better as compared boys schools (Table. 3 & 6).

The results showed a varying degree of media exposure between each group but the score of media exposed children were better in each group. These results were in line with (Zevenbergen & Logan, 2008), (Johnson, 2012), (Powers et al., 2013), (Stanmore et al, 2017), all these researchers agree that computer games have a positive effect on children visual discrimination ability, though every game may not have the same effect (JU & Eun., 2003). Li, (2017), is not of the opinion as he stressed other factors mainly IQ, financial conditions, same viewpoint is shared by (Velicu, and Marinescu, 2019) and (Kim & So, 2012). Taylor et al., (2018) is of the view that no such relation exists neither positive nor negative.

CONCLUSIONS

The study was conducted to investigate the effect of media exposure on visual discrimination ability of elementary school children aged 4-8 years.

1. The results of the present study showed better visual discrimination ability in all age groups, both genders, locality and government and private sector's children who have media and internet exposure.

2. The media exposure in school children of urban for the age group 4-5 years, 6-7 and 7-8 years was better than from rural school children. But the media exposure in children age group 5-6 years was better in rural school children as compared to urban school children.

3. As for as media exposure in government and private schools is concerned, media exposure in the elementary school children of age groups 4-5, 5-6, 6-7 and 7-8 is greater in private schools as compared to government school children.

4. Regarding media exposure in male and female schools, the media exposure for the age group of 4-5, 5-6, 6-7, and 7-8 was better in female children as compared to male elementary school children..

The results of the present study showed better visual discrimination ability in all age groups, both genders, locality and government and private sector's children who have media and internet exposure.

Children who have media exposure have greater scores than the children who have minor media exposure concluding that media exposure have a positive effect on visual discrimination ability.

RECOMMENDATION

This study was conducted to investigate the effect of media exposure on visual discrimination ability of elementary school children of aged 4 – 8 years. The study showed that as the age group increased the visual discrimination ability also increase from lowest to highest level.

The results of the present study showed better visual discrimination ability in all age groups, both genders, locality and government and private sector's children who have media and internet exposure.

So it is recommended that all the schools (public and private) management should make arrangements to expose their student to media and internet irrespective of urban and rural schools.

Poor and needy students should be provided cell phones with internet packages. In this way the visual discrimination ability of the students of age group 4-8 years can be increased.

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